

KOHLBERG'S STAGES OF MORAL DEVELOPMENT AND FACTS STUDY AND MORAL EDUCATION

Specialist Clinical Psychologist Banu Beyaz

St. Clements University Clinical Psychology PhD Student

To cite this article: *Banu Beyaz, St. Clements University, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 6-3, 2022, p. 360-378. - 0099-0001-2207-0208*

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Asst.Prof. Osman Doruk

"• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

process.

"• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

In this study, the concepts of morality, moral development, moral stage, moral dilemma are explained based on the literature. Afterwards, Kohlberg's stages of moral development were introduced, the famous pharmacist dilemma, which he also used in his research, was studied with university students, examples were given from the answers of four cases, and the article was concluded by emphasizing values and ways to encourage moral development. In this context, we can say that morality is the awareness of the individual to choose and use the good and the truth for both himself and the society, and the freedom to act, without experiencing internal conflict. When the studies on morality are examined, the concept of "mature morality" is also encountered in the literature. Trautner (1991) proposes three criteria for mature morality. 1. Internalization of norms: Fulfillment of normative obligations without external control and coercion or compliance with a norm defended by the individual himself. Sensitivity to justice: Awareness and sensitivity of justice about the rules regarding the exchange and sharing of rewards and punishments or resources in a social system 3. Able to withdraw one's own needs and interests - to give up: to give up one's own needs towards others within the framework of mutual responsibility, to show empathy, to help others Experiencing feelings of spiritual satisfaction, such as being satisfied when done. According to Kohlberg, morality; It is a species-specific cognitive structure that includes making conscious judgments and decisions about right-wrong, right-wrong, good-bad, and acting accordingly.

Keywords: *Ethics, Moral Development, Moral Dilemma, Values, Moral Education, Quotations*

1. Introduction

equivalent of the Latin word "moral" (morality-moralitas) . In Arabic, ethics is the plural of the word " hulk " and means temperament, temperament, and creation, and it describes the

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

moral principles that must be followed in human relations, traditionally the values of the society and the rules of behavior. (<http://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Morality>) When considered from a philosophical point of view, Hançerlioğlu (1989) says that morality is "the science that determines and examines the rules of individual and social behavior in a certain period of a certain society" (Hançerlioğlu, 1989). : 89) According to Develioğlu (1986), morality; It is defined as "the science that teaches the procedures and rules that need to be followed in order to do good and avoid evil " (Develioğlu, 1986:20). Güngör's (2003) question what morality can be answered in three ways: 1. To distinguish right from wrong. 2. Acting according to this distinction 3. It means having a sense of dignity in virtuous behavior and the ability to feel guilt or shame for one's actions that violate the standards .(**Güngör ,1993**) In this context, we can say that morality is the awareness of the individual to choose and use the good and the truth for both himself and the society, and the freedom to act, without experiencing internal conflict. When the studies on morality are examined, the concept of "mature morality" is also encountered in the literature. Trautner (1991) proposes three criteria for mature morality. 1. Internalization of norms: Fulfillment of normative obligations without external control and coercion or compliance with a norm defended by the individual himself. 2. Sensitivity to justice: Awareness and sensitivity of justice about the rules regarding the exchange and sharing of rewards and punishments or resources in a social system 3. Able to withdraw one's own needs and interests - to give up: to give up one's own needs towards others within the framework of mutual responsibility, to show empathy, to help others Experiencing feelings of spiritual satisfaction, such as being satisfied when done. According to Kohlberg, morality; It is a species-specific cognitive structure that includes making conscious judgments and decisions about right-wrong, right-wrong, good-bad, and acting accordingly. In other words; Morality, which is a cognitive ability, is the ability of the individual to make judgments, take decisions and act in accordance with the principles determined by himself and while can overlap with universal principles. (Çiftçi, 2003: 43-77) "Moral (moral) development; It is the development of principles and principles that apply to the determination of right and wrong." (Özbay, 1999: 53) Moral development is not the unconditional compliance with all the values of the society, but the process of creating a system of values for social harmony. (Senemoğlu, 1997:68) Moral

development is one of the most essential elements of personality development, and it is related to the individual's developing an awareness of what is good and what is bad in the process of socialization. Along with moral development, a person should be able to control himself within the framework of the rules and traditions of the society. (Kağıtçıbaşı, 1999) Gander and Gardiner focus on three basic aspects of morality : cognitive, behavioral, and emotional. Concepts, values, attitudes are formed by reasoning about right and wrong cognitively. is brought. Behaviorally, the individual may exhibit behaviors that are in line with his own moral reasoning style, sometimes exhibiting behaviors that are the opposite of his own cognitive moral attitudes. Emotionally, people have “feelings” about what is right and wrong, and these emotions can match or contradict their thoughts and behavior . (Gander,MJ . and Gardiner , HW (1998) According to Başaran, “it is the individual's learning of good and right behaviors that are appreciated by the society, starting from the early ages.” (Başaran, 1996) Onur defines moral development as “the process of children acquiring principles that guide them to evaluate certain behaviors as right or wrong and enable them to direct their own actions” (Onur, 1999 : 102). Senemoğlu defines moral development as "the process of creating a system of values in order to ensure an effective adaptation to the society, not a passive harmony despite all the values of the society". (Senemoğlu, 2002:68)

2. Characteristics of Kohlberg's Stage of Moral Development Approach and Concept of Moral Dilemma

The features of Kohlberg's phase approach are:

1. *Stages involve diverse ways of thinking
2. The phases form a successive structure.
3. *Stages form an unchanging order or order in individual development. Cultural factors can accelerate, slow down or stop development, but cannot change the order of development.

The limitations of Kohlberg's theory are that it evaluates moral reasoning rather than observing actual behavior. Another limitation lies in the fact that he generalizes his findings to all people and even to humanity, suggesting the universality of moral stages, even though he mostly conducted his studies with male subjects.

Kohlberg's moral dilemmas contrast values such as law and life. A situation where one-party benefits at the expense of the other is called a dilemma. To determine the moral stages to which moral judgments belong, scenarios containing moral dilemmas are given to individuals and questions such as which behavior is correct and why is correct.

moral dilemma

A moral dilemma arises when an issue has conflicting but arguable right sides" (Sharon, 1991:103)

The process to be followed in the resolution of moral dilemmas consists of the following six stages. (Neil Holmes, 1991 :14.)

- 1- *Identifying relevant events*
- 2- *Identifying professional ethics issues from events*
- 3- *Identifying who is affected by the outcome of the dilemma and how each person or group is affected. ("3 determine who is affected by the outcome of the")*
- 4- *The person who needs to solve the dilemma identifies the appropriate options,*
- 5- *Defining the current result of each option*
- 6- *Deciding on appropriate behavior*

moral judgment skills also have critical-rational negotiation skills;

Instead of immediately opposing and rejecting ideas that do not fit their own ideas, they can listen to them, criticize, and evaluate them, and delay, renew and change their own preliminary

thoughts when necessary . (“Psychological Analysis of Moral Judgment: A Literature Review”)
 (“Psychological Analysis of Moral Judgment: A Literature Review”) (**Farmer, 2003: 44**)

3. Kohlberg's Stages of Moral Development

Kohlberg especially examined moral development in children and reasoning about moral dilemmas, and in this context, he presented a three-level and six-stage moral development model. There are three levels in total, two stages at each level . and societal expectations , finally reaching a level where people use their own moral principles. This developmental process is considered universal and unchangeable in its course. **(5,7,8, 11,15,16,17,18,19)**

Preconventional Level

It is a self-centered moral approach in which the existence of rules developed by others cannot be fully grasped. It lasts until the age of 10, but it is known that some adults have this level of moral understanding.

Stage I: Heteronomous morality; (Avoiding punishment and getting reward)

evaluates events according to their consequences. Whether a behavior is right or wrong is related to how adults see it. There is blind dependence on authority. If adults punish the child’s behavior, it is wrong, if not, it is right. Children obey authority to avoid material and corporal punishment, avoid inflicting corporal punishment on persons and things, and therefore respect the power of those in power . According to people at this stage, Heinz is guilty. The police officers catch him and punish him.

II. Stage : Individualism and self-interested shopping; (Market swap ethics)

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

At this stage, the right thing is to follow the rules if they meet the needs. The reason for doing right is to satisfy their own individual interests and desires. Since the individual understands that everyone is taking care of their own interests, he thinks about his own interests and looks at what will happen in the face of what he does. The important thing here is; to trade fairly, that is, to barter. In other words, the understanding of "take my rose, give my rose" is dominant. At this stage, according to people, Hans is innocent, he stole for his wife, A man should act like this for his wife/husband, because his wife would do the same for him.

Traditional Level

Moral reasoning and judgments are made according to the social order. The effect of a behavior on the social order is considered . The individual is aware of the common feelings, consensus and expectations that come before individual interests . Most individuals are in this stage.

III. Stage : Interpersonal relations and adaptation stage ; (Peer opinion morality)

The purpose of this universe is to be good. There is a desire to "be a good person" both in their own eyes and in other people's eyes. It is right to act in accordance with the expectations of those who are close to the person or certain people such as children, siblings, friends. Because at this stage, the individual wants to be approved by the group he is in . He does not go out of the group to maintain trust , loyalty, and gratitude. According to people at this stage, Heinz is guilty because members of the community blame him for stealing.

IV. Stage : Stage of social conscience ; (Law and order ethics)

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

established social order is accepted without criticism . The purpose of this stage is the preservation of the social order. The law is at the service of the society, the group, and the institution at the same time. In accordance with our conscience, which warns us for the institutions to fulfill their functions and to prevent the collapse of the system, "what would happen if everyone did this?" is considered. For the individual at this stage, discussing the laws and social order and laws means eliminating them . "I close my eyes ; I do my duty." His understanding prevails. According to the people in this stage, which we can also call the social contract stage, Heinz is guilty because he acted against the law, the laws serve to protect the social order and Heinz has disrupted the social order.

The Unconventional Level

At this level, universally valid moral rules, universal values, and legal agreements are preserved. This level, where moral principles and values are defined independently of the people or groups that reveal them, can be reached, or never reached in adolescence or adulthood.

Stage V: Collective agreement, usefulness, individual morality stage

comply with the principles that have been studied and accepted by the society, considering human rights and the benefit of the society. The rules are preserved even if they contradict the rules of the group . While the legal view is accepted, it is believed that laws can be changed to provide more benefits to society. Law and order exist for the good of man. An attempt is made to change a law that does not serve people and harms them, and to question the concepts of life and freedom. According to people in this stage, Heinz is guilty because he violated the agreement made by society. In addition, people must respect each other's private property.

VI. Stage: Universal moral principles stage

The individual follows the ethical principles chosen by him/herself and exhibits behaviors consistent with general moral rules. In this period, right and wrong is the behavior that is in accordance with the moral principles developed by the person's own conscience, not the laws and rules of the social order. These principles include the principles of justice, human rights, and respect for people. Man is above law and order. Man tries to reach the universal good and beauty . According to people at this stage, Heinz is innocent because human life is more important than anything else, if a Human's life is at stake, theft can be committed.

Kohlberg 's scenario involving the famous pharmacist dilemma is as follows: “A woman in Europe is dying from a rare form of cancer. A drug, a form of radium, discovered by a pharmacist in the same city, will be able to save him. The pharmacist charges \$2000, ten times the cost of the medicine. The sick woman's husband, Heinz, can only collect \$1,000 by borrowing money from everyone he knows. Heinz tells the pharmacist that his wife is dying and suggests that he either give the medicine cheaper or give half the money later. But the pharmacist said, “I found this medicine and I want to make money!” says and does not accept Heinz's proposal. Heinz, who is left with no choice, sneaks into the pharmacy one night and steals the medicine...”

Should Heinz steal the drug? Shouldn't it play? Explain your reasons and reasons why you should or should not do this. (Bekent University; 2006; Child and Adolescent Mental Health Course was one of my final questions.)

The moral dilemma story above was given to a group of 24 female students and they were asked to write their answers with justification. 2/3 of the group said “Yes, it is right that Hans steals the medicine because...” 1/3 of the group said “No, Hans should not steal the medicine because....” Below you will examine the answers to five different cases.

4. Four Cases of Different Levels of Moral Judgment

Case 1: 20 Years Old Female Student; stage 5

“My answer is no! The society we live in has certain rules. Everyone must abide by these prohibitions and rules. Because it has been accepted as reasonable by everyone. Theft is an unruly behavior that is considered a crime by the rules of society . No one likes to take their belongings or anything secretly without their permission. Desperation can lead people to misbehavior many times, but no matter what, we must use the brain that belongs to us. The situation we are in should never make us despair. Stealing is also wrong and forbidden in terms of social rules, and it is wrong and forbidden in terms of the rules of the religion we believe in. Anyway, I do not think theft is right. Of course, in every desperation there is a solution. Just be a decent human being. Every door you touch will open for you. If we have a creator, he will see us and reach out. If he does not, he has a point. “No to theft!” I say...”

Case 2: 21-Year-Old Female Student; Phase

“No, this behavior is wrong. Heinz approached the issue emotionally by stealing the drug. In the face of the pharmacist's attitude, he should have explained the situation to the closest relevant authorities and asked them for help in this regard. Relevant authorities may be municipalities, mukhtars or aid organizations, they may be in higher positions. He can even complain about the pharmacist to the necessary places”

Case 3: 20-Year-Old Female Student: A Response Approaching Stage 6

" Yes! This behavior corrects. Because Heinz did not resort to an act of stealing at first . He tried everything he could, he borrowed money, his beloved wife was dying, the pharmacist acted cruelly even though he said the rest of the money. After exhausting all imaginable remedies, it was inevitable that he would steal the drug . but I think many people in Hans' place would have done the same when we empathized. If a person's life ends because of a little money,

it is a deplorable situation. Heinz will also feel very guilty . I do not think he would have stolen the drug if he really did not have to. Therefore, this behavior corrects. Nothing can be more important than human life. and I'm sure he would pay the pharmacist his debt after taking the medicine to his wife."

Case 4: 19-Year-Old Female Student: A Response Approaching Stage 3

"No! This behavior is wrong! His wife may be dying, but that does not mean he should steal . Because Heinz does not want to lose the one, he loves here, and he is being selfish , because he is afraid of being alone . The pharmacist needs this money too, he is guilty."

5. Values and Moral Education

Values are the importance that an individual places on varied factors in his life. (Lamberton ; 1995) Value for the individual

It can also be defined as any thought structure, object or activity that is important. Çelikkaya defined value as "all kinds of social, humanitarian, ideological or divine origin feelings, thoughts, rules or values that are accepted, adopted, kept alive within a society, a belief, an ideology or among people." (1996; p:168)

Many classifications have been made to continue the research on values effectively. The most known and accepted of these classifications are; Nelson, Rokeach , Spranger , and Schwartz. In this study, Spranger is emphasized in terms of its practicality .

Classification of values according to Spranger

Scientific Values: Gives importance to truth, knowledge, reasoning, and critical thinking. People with scientific values are experimental, critical, rational, and intellectual.

Economic Values : It gives importance to the useful and practical. It states that economic values should be considered important in life.

Aesthetic Values : It gives importance to symmetry, harmony, and form. The individual sees life as a variety of events . He thinks that art is a necessity for society.

Social Values: Loving others , helping and not being selfish are essential. The highest value is human love. It offers human love to people. He is kind and sympathetic. It is not selfish.

Political Values : There is personal power, influence, and fame. It is about strength.

Religious Values : It comprehends the universe as a whole and attaches itself to its unity. He sacrifices worldly aspects for the sake of religion. (Akbaş;2004.30-31)

Steps to be Followed in the Process of Gaining Values

1. To choose freely and make independent choices.
2. Choosing among alternatives after evaluating a range of choices available.
3. Choosing the possible outcomes of each alternative after mental filtering.
4. Disclosure of values found to be the most important and most valuable.
5. Explanation of selected values.
6. Demonstrate a behavior consistent with the chosen values.
7. Repetition of the behavior. (Akbaş, 2004:74)

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Ways to Promote Moral Development

can be done for young people to reach higher moral development stages of students ?

It should be ensured that they are in mutual communication with each other; To ensure that the desired values are reflected by using examples of life, stories, and biographies related to honor, dignity, virtue, to encourage students to do social services, to reward them with praise and appreciation when they show care and virtuous behavior, to correct ethical and unethical disrespectful behaviors, First of all, it is important to be a good model with positive personal examples.

Another important way to encourage moral development is to present students with moral contradiction situations, moral dilemmas. In this way, they will be able to struggle for moral reasoning with the moral values they already have, and it will be possible to gain more appropriate and skillful lives with this internal struggle and evaluation. It is also helpful to use and discuss quotes, sayings, aphorisms.

The total of the individual; To support and discuss their emotional-social-moral-mental development, firstly, examples of stories containing moral dilemmas are given below, and finally, aphorisms about "morality" are mentioned.

Stories with Moral Dilemmas

Story 1 : *"A prisoner is in jail for theft. He was sentenced to 10 years, but several years*

Then he escapes from prison and settles in a new city under another name. Eight years of intense

He saves money to work and start his own business. He treats his customers fairly, and his workers are well paid.

gives. Most of his earnings are invested in charities. However, one day old

his neighbor realizes that he is the man who escaped from the police eight years ago and is sought by the police."

Should the neighbor report this man to the police? Shouldn't it? Explain with reasons...

Story 2: *"An employer owns a gas station. He needs an expert to help him.*

Good experts have power. The best of the applicants is a Romani person. Employer against Romani people

Although he is not prejudiced, many of his clients are reluctant to hire him because they do not like Romani people.

If this Romani person starts working, his clients may prefer to do business elsewhere. what is this?

So, the employer decides to tell this expert that he has found someone else. However, this is as adept as Romani person

He has not hired anyone yet because he could not find anyone. ”

What should the employer do? He should or should not hire a Romani person... Please explain your preference with reasons.

Story 3: *“A woman is dying of cancer and there is another known medical method to save her. there is no more. The doctor knows that the woman has six months to live. The woman is very weak. I can take some*

The painkiller he took would be able to kill him. The woman is mad with pain. In her quiet moments, she begs the doctor to give her enough morphine to kill her. He cannot take this pain any longer because there are only a few months left.

He says he wants to die. ”

What should the doctor do? Should he give morphine? Shouldn't he? Please explain your opinion with reasons.

(Sample stories are taken from the test “Identification of Values.”)

Examples of Quotations on Morality

“Religion and denomination are a matter left to everyone's conscience. No one can force anyone to accept a religion, or a sect. Religion and sect are never used as a policy tool. ”

Mustafa Kemal Atatürk

“ Creation forgives , because of the Creator ”

Yunus Emre

“No legacy is as rich as honesty”

William Shakespeare

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

“There are many religions; but there is only one morality.”

John Ruskin

“Good means two things, one is absolute good, and the other is what is good for someone”

Aristotle

“Do not do to others what you do not want done to you” (“Do not do to others what you don’t want to be done to you - Keats School”)

Confucius

“The gentleman must be chaste, mild-mannered and of noble nature.”

Yusuf Has Hacip

“The gentleman should not make mischief. Because of this act, wealth will be lost.”

Yusuf Has Hacip

“The law is written in the hearts of the people.”

st. Augustine

“What is left when honor is lost?”

Publius Syrus

“Where did you wear out the gem of your eye, where did you use your five senses?”

Mevlana

“I see myself as the horsefly that God infested the state”

Socrates

“When you measure, measure exactly and use the right balance”

Quran, Isra:35 ; To:181-182

“The right scales and the scales are from your Lord”

Torah; Proverbs of Solomon , 16:11

“Love your neighbor as yourself.”

Bible, Matthew, 19:19

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

*“Policy says “be smart as snakes;” morality is “wise like snakes, like doves”
be harmless.” “*

Immanuel Kant

“I am looking for an honest person.”

Diogenes of Sinop

“Mesned-i izzetteserefranz who stole with a million

A few cents are a shovel for the dissenters .”

Ziya Pasha

“Do not apply to anyone what is hard for your soul”

Haji Bektashi Veli

“Be loyal to the truth, be fair to the people”

Haji Bektashi Veli

“The curve does not suit Erenler Square”

Yunus Emre

*“Lords and folks, know well that the Republic of Turkey cannot be a land of sheikhs, dervishes, disciples, and madmen. The most accurate, most genuine cult, cult of civilization.”
Mustafa Kemal Atatürk*

“Can a civilized nation be viewed as a mass of people who are dragged behind some sheikhs, dedes, sayyids, chalabis , fathers, dervishes and who secure their fortunes and lives to fortune-tellers, magicians, and healers?”

Mustafa Kemal Atatürk

“ A teacher who does not look at seventy -two nations with one eye are a rebel against the truth.”

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Yunus Emre

"Come, let's meet, let's make things easy, let's love, let's be loved, no one will be left in the world"

Yunus Emre

FOOTNOTES AND REFERENCES

Adair , J. (2000) Decision Making and Problem Solving . Translated by Nurdan Kalaycı. Ankara. Gazi Bookstore

Akbas, he. (2004) The Affective Purposes (Values) of the Turkish National Education System in Primary Education

Aktan.C . Words on Religion and Morals:
<http://www.yergi.net/news/652.html>

Basaran. I.E. (1996) Educational Psychology. Ankara. Rose Publishing House

Black Poplar Sycamore. G. (2006) Comparison of University Students' Moral Judgment Abilities and Moral Judgment Abilities and Self-Actualization Levels. Master's thesis, C. U. Adana

Çelikkaya H. (1996) Functional Education Sociology. Istanbul. Alpha Publications

Determination of Values Test; p:146-150

Develioğlu, F. (1986) Ottoman Turkish-Turkish Encyclopedic Dictionary. Ankara Aydin Bookstore. Number:20

Development and Behavior , Theory ” Research and social Issues . (Ed:T . Lickona) New York . Holt

Dicle Un. ed . fac. der. Ziya Gokalp Educ . fac. Magazine, issue:5, p:73-86

Evaluation of the Level of Realization in the Second Level . Unpublished Doctoral Thesis. Gazi University, Ankara.

Farmer, N. (2003) Kohlberg's Theory of Cognitive Moral Development. Journal of Values Education 1(1) 43-77

Farmer, N. (2003) Kohlberg's Theory of Cognitive Moral Development. Journal of Values Education, p.44

Gander, MJ . and Gardiner , HW (1998)
Child and Adolescent Development .Trans.
a.

Hançerlioğlu, O. (1989) Philosophy
Dictionary, Istanbul. Remzi
Bookstore.say:89

<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Morality>

Kagıtcıbası, C. (1999) Man and People.
Istanbul. Evolution Publications.

KILIÇ MUSTAFA. (2005) Anadoluyan
Therapy's (Anatolian Therapy)
Introducing. 21*23

Kılıç, M.(2008) “ Introducing Anatolian
Therapy” İnönü University, Faculty of
Education, Educational Sciences.

Kohlberg L. (1976) “Moral Stages and
moralization _the cognitive developmental
Appoch in Morale

Mercin, L. (2005) “Comparison of Piaget
and Kohlberg's Moral Development
Theories and Characteristics”

Neil Holmes, " Resolution of Ethical
Conflict ", Management Accounting,
December 1991, p.14.

Onur, B. (1991) Developmental Psychology
. Adulthood, Old Age, Death. Ankara.
Image Bookstore, p:102

Özbay, Y. (1999) Developmental and
Learning Psychology. Ankara. Empathy
Publications, number:53

Psychology of Values . The Netherlands .
Academics Union Foundation Spring.
No: 8 Amsterdam

Rinehart and Winston. 33-47

Senemoglu, N. (1997) Developmental
Learning and Teaching . Ankara . Ertem
Publishing. Number:68

Senemoglu, N. (2002) Developmental
Learning and Teaching. Ankara. Q:68

September 2005. VIII. National
Psychological Counseling and Guidance
Congress, Marmara University

Sharon E: STANFORD, Ethics , Internal
auditor June 1991, p.103.

Yapıcı, Ş. & Yapıcı, M . (2005) Moral
Development in Child. Journal of
University and Society, vol:5, no:3